

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SOLUTION TO THE PROBLEM OF OPTIMIZATION OF A CATALYTIC REFORMING UNIT

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Abstract

The refining, petroleum separation and petrochemical industries have high demands on the quantity and quality of the resulting products, which leads to increased process complexity both technologically and structurally. The complexity of control also affects the complexity of the process structure. In such a situation, it is considered appropriate to control the process under optimal conditions.

In the presented paper, an algorithm for solving an optimization problem based on a mathematical model of the reactor block of a catalytic reforming unit has been developed. This algorithm ensures the conduct of the technological process in the optimal operating mode and the optimal value of the control parameters.

Keywords: catalytic reforming unit, reactor block, regression equation, objective function

Introduction

Perfect study and mastering of technological processes continuously running in complex technological complexes is considered to be one of the important stages of creating optimal control systems. In modern conditions it is necessary to create new, more perfect control systems to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of production in the oil industry, as well as to change the quality indicators of products based on the necessary requirements.

When we talk about optimization of technological processes, it means the optimal conditions for the implementation of the process in question. Optimization is an activity aimed at obtaining optimal indicators taking into account the specified conditions of limitations. Before performing optimization, it is important to select an optimization criterion. Depending on the current states, economic (for example, minimum cost price of production), technological, etc. criteria can be used as optimization criteria. The objective function is the basis of the selected optimization criterion, which expresses the dependence between the optimization criterion and the parameters that affect its value. As a result, the extremum of the objective function is found and determined by means of the optimization problem [1,2].

At the same time, the presence of a number of specific characteristics of such technological systems makes it difficult to solve the issues of their management. Examples of such characteristics are a wide range of regime parameters, large measurement errors of individual parameters, and in some cases the lack of operational means of monitoring their measurement, uncontrolled change in parameters, changes in process characteristics and non-linearity, as well as other features.

In general, we assume that the objective function is given in the following form [3,4]:

$$F=f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

This function can be linear, a differential equation, nonlinear, or in other forms.

x_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) - the variables can be expressed in terms of constraints in the both form : equal as well as inequality :

$$\varphi_i(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = 0 \quad i = \overline{1, m}$$

$$\varphi_i(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \geq 0 \quad i = \overline{1, k}$$

The main task of the platforming section of the catalytic reforming unit is to increase the octane number of gasoline obtained in the primary oil refining unit. If the octane number of the catalyst in this process is below the norm, some problems arise. This may be due to low temperatures at the inlet of the platforming reactors, increased pressure in the reactors, as well as a change in the quality of the feedstock (a decrease in the total amount of naphthenic hydrocarbons, a decrease in the boiling point). To eliminate these reasons, the pressure in the system should be reduced to 2-5 kg / cm² and the temperature of the gas product mixture should be lowered. It may happen that the octane number is below the norm or above. The reason for this is an increase in the volumetric velocity of the feedstock and mixing of the feedstock with the reaction products due to leaks in the tube bundles in the gas-feedstock heat exchangers. To solve this problem, it is necessary to repair the heat exchangers during the plant shutdown, reduce the feedstock feed and increase the temperature in the reactors.

Solving of the problem

Let's find the optimal values of the parameters affecting the reactor, which is the main apparatus of the hydrotreating block of catalytic reforming unit. The 1 solution for the optimization problem for the reactor unit of the catalytic reforming complex was found using the mathematical software package MathCAD. The optimization problem is solved by entering the coefficients of the mathematical model of the reactor and the constraint conditions based on the objective function [5,6].

Main regime parameters of the reactor block :
 X_1 - DR -111 temperature of the gas product mixture entering the hydrotreating reactor $^{\circ}\text{S}$
 X_2 - DR -111 temperature at the bottom of the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor $^{\circ}\text{S}$
 X_3 - DR -111 pressure in the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor kg/sm^2
 Y - DR -111 gas consumption in the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor/ saat

Constraint conditions for input and control parameters:

$$365^{\circ}\text{S} \leq X_1 \leq 374^{\circ}\text{S}$$

$$305^{\circ}\text{S} \leq X_2 \leq 310^{\circ}\text{S}$$

$$10,8 \text{ kg}/\text{sm}^2 \leq X_3 \leq 11,5 \text{ kg}/\text{sm}^2$$

$$136 \text{ t}/\text{h} \leq y \leq 138 \text{ t}/\text{h}$$

Regression equation in linear form:

$$Y = B_0 + B_1 X_1 + B_2 X_2 + B_3 X_3$$

Consumption of gas obtained in the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor -F, t/h

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3) \longrightarrow \max$$

$$Y = 220,7340 - 0,09398 X_1 - 0,30364 X_2 + 1,16309 X_3$$

$$b_0 := 220.734059$$

$$b_1 := -0.009398$$

$$b_2 := -0.303646$$

$$b_3 := 1.163097$$

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) := b_0 + b_1 \cdot x_1 + b_2 \cdot x_2 + b_3 \cdot x_3$$

$$x_1 := 365$$

$$x_2 := 305$$

$$x_3 := 10.8$$

Given

$$365 \leq x_1 \leq 374$$

$$305 \leq x_2 \leq 310$$

$$10.8 \leq x_3 \leq 11.5$$

$$p := \text{Maximize}(f, x_1, x_2, x_3)$$

$$p = \begin{pmatrix} 365 \\ 305 \\ 11.5 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 137.253$$

The optimal values of temperature of the gas product mixture entering the hydrotreating reactor 365°S , temperature at the bottom of the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor 305°S , pressure in the DR-111 hydrotreating reactor $11,5 \text{ kg}/\text{sm}^2$. Consequently the optimal value of gas flow rate in the hydrotreating reactor is $F=137,25 \text{ t/h}$.

Conclusion

Mathematical formalization of the issue of optimal control of the reactor block of the catalytic cracking is performed. An optimization algorithm is developed that allows to calculate the optimal operating modes of the reactor block. Values obtained as a result of solving the optimization problem for reactor block.

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